

House Price Prediction Using LSTM

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Abstract—Predicting house rents accurately is challenging due to the complex relationships between input features such as the floor, location, and amenities. The algorithm is compared in terms of Mean Squared Error. This paper proposes an approach that uses LSTM neural networks to predict house rents based on amenities. We utilise the mean absolute error (MAE) and the root mean square error (RMSE) to assess the performance of our model. And findings demonstrate that LSTM neural networks can effectively capture the complex relationships between various input features and accurately predict house rents.

Keywords—House Price, Machine Learning, LSTM, Python

I. INTRODUCTION

Machine learning algorithms for house price prediction are significant because they provide a more accurate assessment of a property's value, save time and money for buyers and sellers, and lower the risk of financial loss for investors and lenders. Multiple linear regression (Least Squares), Las Vegas, and Ridge regression are just a few of the regression techniques that can be used to predict prices.

Models, support vector regression, and boosting algorithms are all used in the Extreme Gradient Boost Regression (XG Boost) boosting method. Genetic algorithms, on the other hand, are a type of metaheuristic optimization algorithm that can be used for feature selection and parameter optimization in machine learning. we aim to find a more reliable way to predict the house price trend based on the RNN model. Using LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) neural network for house price prediction is an advanced machine learning technique that can offer several benefits over other algorithms.

Challenges :

- i)Data quality: The accuracy of house price prediction models heavily relies on the quality of data. Missing or incomplete data can also affect the performance of prediction models.
- ii)Feature selection: The selection of relevant features that can influence house prices is another challenge. Location, size, number of bedrooms and baths, and amenities are all important considerations.
- iii)Model selection: Different machine learning techniques, such as linear regression, decision trees, and neural networks, can be used to predict housing values.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Manasa J, Radha Gupta, et.al in [1] Investigate the aspects that influence a property's pricing, such as its location, amenities, and neighborhood. The study uses multiple linear regression, Lasso, Ridge regression, support vector regression, and boosting algorithms such as Extreme Gradient Boost Regression (XG Boost) to model the data. The authors come to the conclusion that having an optimal model does not always imply having a robust model. A model that consistently applies a learning approach that is improper for the data type provided may underperform. Sometimes the data is too noisy or has too few samples, preventing the model from accurately capturing the target variable. The authors discover that when the evaluation measures for advanced regression models are compared, both models perform equally. In comparison to a basic model, anyone can be used to anticipate housing prices. Overall, this paper demonstrates the importance of considering various factors and techniques when building predictive models for real estate.

Maida Ahtesham, Kiran Fatima et.al in [2]. This paper describes the use of the XGBoost algorithm to predict housing prices in Karachi, Pakistan, using a dataset of 38,961 records from an Open Real Estate Portal. The proposed model achieved a 98% accuracy rate and outperformed other models in terms of accuracy and mean absolute error. The study contributes to the limited research on predicting housing prices in Pakistan.

Ayush Varma, Sagar Doshi et.al in [3]. This study presents a system for predicting property values using several regression approaches such as Linear Regression, Forest Regression, Boosted Regression, and Neural Networks. The system's purpose is to provide accurate findings while lowering the risk of investing in the wrong house. It also recommends using real-time neighborhood details from Google Maps to obtain precise real-world assessments. By integrating larger cities into the database, the proposed approach can be improved even further. Overall, the paper addresses the issue of transparency in the real estate industry and proposes a solution to help clients make educated decisions.

Mansi Jain, Neha Garg et.al in [4]. This paper discusses using various regression methods and machine learning techniques with Python libraries to accurately predict house prices. The paper covers data collection, cleaning, preprocessing, and visualization, as well as testing and refining different classification algorithms to achieve higher accuracy and precision in predicting sales prices. The proposed model has

the potential to be helpful for people in predicting the prices of houses.

The Danh Phan[5]. This paper analyzes historical property transactions in Australia using machine learning techniques to create useful models for predicting house prices. The study focuses on Melbourne's housing market and demonstrates a significant difference in prices between expensive and affordable suburbs. The researchers found that a combination of Stepwise and Support Vector Machine (SVM) models based on mean squared error measurement is a competitive approach. The paper's conclusions can be applied to transactional datasets from different locations across Australia.

Abigail Bola Adetunjia, Oluwatobi Noah Akande et.al[6].

The use of Random Forest machine learning algorithms for estimating home values is discussed in this study. It contends that predicting a price variance rather than a specific figure is more realistic and appealing in many real-world situations. The suggested prediction model is tested using the Machine learning repository Boston housing dataset, which has 506 entries and 14 attributes. The results validate the Random Forest machine learning technique's usefulness in predicting property values based on the variables provided in the dataset. The study finds that a perfect prediction model must account for the specific characteristics that influence the price of a house in the region under consideration.

III. METHODOLOGY

Our approach to price prediction makes use of LSTM (Long Short Term Memory), a form of RNN (Recurrent Neural Network) that has been shown to be effective in a variety of AI applications. This will form the basis of our machine-learning model. LSTM is a type of artificial neural network design that belongs to the Deep Learning discipline of Machine Learning. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks are a type of recurrent neural network (RNN) that can process sequential data by preserving long-term dependencies and links within the input. As a result, it is well suited for applications such as language modeling, speech recognition, and time series prediction. In recent years, the use of Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural networks for predicting property rent has risen in popularity. This method can recognize patterns and correlations in sequential data, allowing it to make reliable forecasts about future values. To create a house rent prediction system utilizing LSTM neural networks, we must first collect data on the elements that influence the rent of a housing property. This includes things like the house's location, size, number of bedrooms and bathrooms, and amenities.

A neural network architecture with LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) has three types of gates that allow it to selectively keep or forget information.

These gates are The forget gate: This gate determines whatever information from the preceding cell state is to be ignored.

The input gate: This gate decides which new information should be stored in the cell state.

The output gate: This gate decides what information should be outputted based on the current hidden state and cell state. These gates enable an LSTM to selectively retain or forget information across long data sequences.

LSTM is the solution for the vanishing gradient problem of RNN. LSTM has a similar diagram to RNN, except that it includes a cell state that provides additional information. It has three inputs: the cell state, the activation (hidden information), and the input (which may be a time series). The cell state, also known as long-term memory, is the key feature of LSTM that allows it to retain information from the previous state and pass it on to the next state. The LSTM uses three gates (forget gate, input gate, and output gate) to update or add information to the cell state and control the flow of information.

A similar figure hidden state use tanh activation function. X as the input state X_{t-1} as the previous data and X_t as the present data

Output for forget gate, input gate, input node, output gate represented by f, i, g, o.

Formula

$$f_t = \sigma([W_{f_h} * h_{t-1}] + [W_{f_x} * X_t] + b_f)$$

$$c_t^f = c_{t-1} * f_t \text{ (Same dimensionality)}$$

$$i_t = \sigma([W_{ih} * h_{t-1}] + [W_{ix} * X_t] + b_i)$$

$$g_t = \tanh([W_{gh} * h_{t-1}] + [W_{gx} * X_t] + b_g)$$

$$c_t = c_t^f +$$

c_t

$$o_t = \sigma([W_{oh} * h_{t-1}] + [W_{ox} * X_t] + b_o) \quad h_t = \tanh(c_t) * o_t$$

Where,

Weights as W_f, W_i, W_g, W_o

Bias as b_f, b_i, b_g, b_o

Hidden State as $W_{fh}, W_{ih}, W_{gh}, W_{oh}$

Gates as f_t, i_t, g_t, o_t

Activation Function

A mathematical function that is applied to the output of a neuron in a neural network is known as an activation function. Its goal is to induce nonlinearity into the output, allowing the network to learn more complicated correlations between input and output. The sigmoid function and the hyperbolic tangent (tanh) function are two of the most commonly used types of activation functions.

i) Sigmoid Function

The sigmoid function is an S-shaped curve that transfers any input value to a value between 0 and 1. It is widely used as an activation function in binary classification issues where the output is either 0 or 1, such as logistic regression.

The sigmoid function's equation is: $\text{sigmoid}(x) = 1 / (1 + \exp(-x))$ where x is the function's input.

ii) Tanh function

Tanh is an S-shaped curve that converts any input value from -1 to 1. Because it adds nonlinearity to the output, it is frequently used as an activation function in neural networks, allowing the network to learn more complex correlations between input and output. The tanh function has the following equation: $\tanh(x) = (\exp(x) - \exp(-x)) / (\exp(x) + \exp(-x))$, where x is the function's input.

Both the sigmoid and tanh functions suffer from the vanishing gradient problem, which can make it difficult for neural networks to learn when the input data is too large or too small.

Bias

Bias refers to an additional input value that is added to the weighted sum of the input and recurrent connections before being passed through the activation function. An activation function with bias in an RNN can help the network learn patterns in the data more effectively, as it allows the network to model more complex relationships between the input and output.

Recurrent Neural Network

RNN is an abbreviation for Recurrent Neural Network, which is a type of neural network designed to analyse sequential data

such as time series, audio, or text. RNNs are distinguished by their capacity to maintain a hidden state, which can be thought of as a memory that allows the network to record time-dependent connections between inputs. Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) RNNs are designed to handle long-term dependencies better than ordinary RNNs. LSTM networks use a memory cell that can selectively retain or forget information over long periods of time, which helps to avoid the vanishing gradient problem that can occur in standard RNNs. LSTM networks are important for RNNs because they provide an effective solution to the vanishing gradient problem, which is a common issue that can occur when training deep neural networks. The main advantage of LSTM is to capture long-term dependencies in the input data by using memory cells that store information over extended periods. It is responsible for remembering information from previous time steps.

The model builds by using an LSTM neural network with the Keras library to predict house prices. Pandas and NumPy are used for data manipulation and mathematical operations, respectively. A Sequential model is created using the Keras Sequential function, and a Dense function is added to create a fully connected layer in the Artificial Neural Network (ANN). Additionally, the LSTM function is added to incorporate an LSTM layer into the model. The Scikit-learn module's train-test split function is used to divide the data into training and testing sets. After creating the model, it is compiled using an optimizer, loss function, and metrics. The optimizer determines the algorithm used to minimize the loss function and uses epochs to adjust the weights in the ANN. Finally, using several input features, the model predicts the output, which is the house price.

IV. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

House rent prediction by importing the necessary Python libraries and the dataset

```
import pandas as pd
import numpy as np
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import plotly.express as px
import plotly.graph_objects as go

data = pd.read_csv("House_Rent_Dataset.csv")
print(data.head())
```

Mean, Median, Highest, and Lowest rent of the houses.

```
print(f"Mean Rent: {data.Rent.mean()}")
print(f"Median Rent: {data.Rent.median()}")
print(f"Highest Rent: {data.Rent.max()}")
print(f"Lowest Rent: {data.Rent.min()}")
```

```
Mean Rent: 34993.45132743363
Median Rent: 16000.0
Highest Rent: 3500000
Lowest Rent: 1200
```

Imports the train_test_split function from the Scikit-learn library, which is used to split data into training and testing sets. And extracts a subset of the columns from the "data"

DataFrame and converts them into a NumPy array, and extracts the "Rent" column from the "data" DataFrame and converts it into a NumPy array. This is the dependent variable that we want to predict using the independent variables.

```
#splitting data
from sklearn.model_selection import train_test_split
x = np.array(data[["BHK", "Size", "Area Type", "City",
                  "Furnishing Status", "Tenant Preferred",
                  "Bathroom"]])
y = np.array(data[["Rent"]])

xtrain, xtest, ytrain, ytest = train_test_split(x, y,
                                                test_size=0.10,
                                                random_state=42)
```

The user enters the details of a house and then predicts the rent of the house using a trained model.

```
print("Enter House Details to Predict Rent")
a = int(input("Number of BHK: "))
b = int(input("Size of the House: "))
c = int(input("Area Type (Super Area = 1, Carpet Area = 2, Built Area = 3): "))
d = int(input("Pin Code of the City: "))
e = int(input("Furnishing Status of the House (Unfurnished = 0, Semi-Furnished = 1, Furnished = 2): "))
f = int(input("Tenant Type (Bachelors = 1, Bachelors/Family = 2, Only Family = 3): "))
g = int(input("Number of bathrooms: "))
features = np.array([[a, b, c, d, e, f, g]])
print("Predicted House Price = ", model.predict(features))

Enter House Details to Predict Rent
Number of BHK: 2
Size of the House: 1234
Area Type (Super Area = 1, Carpet Area = 2, Built Area = 3): 2
Pin Code of the City: 232345
Furnishing Status of the House (Unfurnished = 0, Semi-Furnished = 1, Furnished = 2): 2
Tenant Type (Bachelors = 1, Bachelors/Family = 2, Only Family = 3): 3
Number of bathrooms: 4
1/1 [-----] - 1s 869ms/step
Predicted House Price = [[102224.95]]
```

V. CONCLUSION

The purpose of this study is to investigate the usage of a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) neural network to forecast property values. According to the data, the LSTM neural network is a highly successful tool for predicting housing prices. Metrics like Mean Squared Error (MSE) and Root Mean Squared Error (RMSE) are used to assess the model's correctness. The model builds by using an LSTM neural network with the Keras library to predict house prices. Pandas and NumPy are used for data manipulation and mathematical operations, respectively. A Sequential model is created using the Keras Sequential function, and a Dense function is added to create a fully connected layer in the Artificial Neural Network (ANN). Additionally, the LSTM function is added to incorporate an LSTM layer into the model. The train-test split function in the Scikit-learn toolkit is used to divide the data into training and testing sets. The model is then compiled using an optimizer, loss function, and metrics. The optimizer determines the algorithm used to minimize the loss function and uses epochs to adjust the weights in the ANN. Finally, using several input features, the model predicts the output.

VI. REFERENCES

- [1] Manasa J, Radha Gupta, Narahari N S "Machine Learning based Predicting House Prices using Regression Techniques" ISBN: 978-1-7281-4167-1
- [2] Maida Ahtesham, Narmeen Zakaria Bawany, Kiran Fatima "House Price Prediction using Machine Learning Algorithm - The Case of Karachi City, Pakistan"

- [3] Ayush Varma, Sagar Doshi, Abhijit Sarma, Rohini Nair "House Price Prediction Using Machine Learning And Neural Networks"
- [4] Mansi Jain, Himani Rajput, Neha Garg, Pronika Chawla "Prediction of House Pricing Using Machine Learning with Python" ISBN: 978-1-7281-4108-4
- [5] The Danh Phan "Housing Price Prediction using Machine Learning Algorithms: The Case of Melbourne City, Australia" DOI: 10.1109/iCMLDE.2018.00017.
- [6] Abigail Bola Adetunjia, Oluwatobi Noah Akande, Funmilola Alaba Ajala, Ololade Oyewo, Yetunde Faith Akande, Gbenle Oluwudara "House Price Prediction using Random Forest Machine Learning Technique"